

COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF METHODS FOR TREATMENT OF UROLITHIASIS

Otakulov Gayratzhon Olimzhonovich
Akbaraliev Ismoilzhon Valisher Ugli

Central Asian Medical University,
Fergana, Uzbekistan.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18738206>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 19th February 2026

Accepted: 20th February 2026

Online: 21st February 2026

KEYWORDS

*urolithiasis, urinary system,
predictor, lifestyle, metabolism,
prevention.*

ABSTRACT

Urolithiasis is a condition in which fine-grained sand and stones (calculi) form in the urinary tract. As the disease progresses, the stones can increase in size, reaching significant sizes.

Studies have shown that approximately 3% of the population faces this problem annually. Older men (30 to 60 years old) are particularly at risk, with urolithiasis occurring approximately three times more often than women. Furthermore, infectious and inflammatory processes in the urinary tract have recently become increasingly common in young children and adolescents.

Introduction. In recent decades, stone removal methods have evolved toward minimally invasive interventions. Extracorporeal shock wave lithotripsy (ESWL) and contact ureterolithotripsy (CULT) are the two main approaches in treating ureteral stones up to 2 cm in size. Despite their widespread use, controversy remains in the literature regarding which procedure provides better clinical efficacy with minimal risks.

A study of trends up to 2019 revealed a steady increase in the incidence of urolithiasis among the population, primarily among individuals aged 30-60. Russian sources more often report urolithiasis in general, rather than urethral stones specifically. However, it is known that approximately 30-40% of all urological hospitalizations are associated with urolithiasis, which indirectly reflects the widespread clinical significance of stone formation.

The prevalence of urolithiasis in Uzbekistan as a whole is estimated at approximately 2%-8% of the population, varying by region: 2-3% in the Fergana Valley, 6-8% or more in the Bukhara and Khorezm regions. When assessing the prevalence of urethral stones in Uzbekistan, less open sources are available. It is believed that urethral stones constitute a significant proportion of symptomatic cases of urolithiasis.

When studying the prevalence of urolithiasis in Europe, a review of epidemiological data indicates that between 5% and 9% of the European population lives with urolithiasis, with differences across countries and climate zones. Prevalence rates vary across European countries, for example, in Germany (4-4.7%), Spain (5.6%), the UK (11.2%), and others.

The relevance of the study is determined by the need to rationally select a treatment method based on stone characteristics and the patient's clinical status. The lack of uniform

recommendations for the use of SWL and ULT requires a comparative analysis based on real clinical data.

Purpose of the study. To conduct a comparative assessment of the effectiveness of extracorporeal lithotripsy and contact ureterolithotripsy in patients with ureteral stones measuring 5-15 mm.

Materials and methods. A prospective cohort study was conducted at the Fergana Urology Center. A total of 200 patients with ureteral stones were included: Group 1 (ESL) - 100 patients; Group 2 (CULT) - 100 patients. Patients ranged in age from 18 to 75 years, with a mean age of 47.2 ± 12.8 years. Stones were located in the proximal, middle, or distal third of the urethra.

We used the following treatment methods: extracorporeal shock wave lithotripsy (ESL) performed using a standard ULT device, and contact ureterolithotripsy (CULT) performed through a ureteroscope with a laser or ultrasound lithotripter. Statistical analysis utilized the χ^2 and Student's t-test; significance was considered at $p < 0.05$.

Results and discussion. In this study, ULT demonstrated higher efficacy than ESWL, especially for stones >10 mm ($p < 0.05$). For stones of 5–9 mm, the differences between the methods were less pronounced, which is consistent with data from several European and Russian studies in recent years.

The study identified possible reasons for this. For larger stones, the external beam lithotripsy mechanism becomes less effective due to limited transmural energy distribution. The contact method provides direct energy delivery to the stone, improving fragmentation.

Complications occurred in both groups, but their frequency was not statistically different ($p = 0.27$). The most common complications were temporary hematuria and dysuria, requiring only symptomatic treatment. Hospitalization was somewhat longer in the ULT group, due to the invasiveness of the procedure and the need for anesthesia.

Conclusions:

1. Contact ureterolithotripsy is more effective than extracorporeal shockwave lithotripsy for ureteral stones measuring 10-15 mm.
2. For stones measuring 5-9 mm, both techniques demonstrate comparable efficacy.
3. Developing treatment algorithms should take into account stone size, location, and local resources.
4. Further multicenter research is needed to refine optimal treatment strategies.

References:

1. Акилов Ф.А., Худайбергенов У.А., Абдукаримов О.О. “Минеральная вода “Зангиота” в лечение и профилактике мочекаменная болезни”: Методические рекомендации Ташкент 2023г. ст 28-29.
2. Xiang, H., et al. Systematic review and meta-analysis of the diagnostic accuracy of low-dose computed tomography of the kidneys, ureters and bladder for urolithiasis.
3. J Med Imaging Radiat Oncol, 2017. 61: 582. 6. Somani, B.K., et al. Review on diagnosis and management of urolithiasis in pregnancy: an ESUT practical guide for urologists. World J Urol, 2017. 35: 1637.
4. Отакулов, Г. (2025). РОЛЬ МИНЕРАЛЬНОГО СОСТАВА ВОДЫ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ МОЧЕКАМЕННОЙ БОЛЕЗНИ У НАСЕЛЕНИЯ ФЕРГАНЫ. В АCADEMIC RESEARCH IN

MODERN SCIENCE (Т. 4, Выпуск 20, сс. 47–50). Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15300251>

5. Отакулов, Г. (2025). МОЧЕКАМЕННАЯ БОЛЕЗНЬ У ЖИТЕЛЕЙ ФЕРГАНСКОЙ ДОЛИНЫ: РЕГИОНАЛЬНЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ, ФАКТОРЫ РИСКА И ПРОФИЛАКТИЧЕСКИЕ МЕРЫ. *Естественные науки в современном мире: теоретические и практические исследования*, 4(5), 113–115. извлечено от <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/zdtf/article/view/50176>

